

Enhanced mathematics performance following spatial skills training using the online learning platform RIF3.0 within the mathematics classroom

Eleni Lagoudaki¹, Günter Maresch¹, Marianna Pagkratidou²

¹Department of Mathematics, University of Salzburg, ²School of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Technological University Dublin

Previous studies on digital spatial training programmes have not always exhibited transfer to mathematics performance. In the present study, we investigated the effects of a digital training intervention, which targeted a variety of spatial skills, on students' performance on a variety of mathematics topics. Following a pre-post quasi-experimental design, 12-13 year-old students in an Austrian school participated in eight spatial training sessions during their mathematics classes through the online spatial thinking training platform RIF3.0, while students in the control classes received regular mathematics instructions. We measured students' arithmetical, place value, geometry, and word problem-solving skills following the Austrian mathematics curriculum guidelines. The preliminary results showed that students in the intervention classes improved their accuracy in arithmetical and geometry tasks, while students in the control classes did not show any improvement. These findings suggest that broader digital spatial training might lead to curriculum-based mathematics improvement.

Keywords: spatial ability, mathematics performance, online learning, RIF3.0

Introduction

There have been studies which demonstrate that digital spatial training transfers to mathematics performance (Hawes et al., 2022). For example, in a lab setting, Gilligan et al. (2020) found that eight-year-old students who received mental-rotation spatial training through instructional videos, improved in missing-term problems. However, in a school setting, Hawes et al. (2015) found that computerized mental-rotation training did not affect 6-8-year-old students' calculation skills. While previous studies focused on training one specific spatial skill to examine transferability in one particular mathematics topic, we aimed to train a broader range of spatial skills, based on the holistic spatial thinking model by Maresch & Sorby (2021). Our goal was to train students in a variety of spatial skills that they could subsequently utilize when solving mathematics tasks in areas such as arithmetic, place value, geometry, and other word-problem tasks. To achieve that, by use of the online spatial training platform RIF3.0 (*RIF 3.0 Home*, n.d.), we trained participants in a combination of spatial skills: visualization, form constancy, position in space, transformation in space, and object combination (Maresch & Sorby, 2021). We specifically examined whether the broad in-mathematics-class spatial training intervention transferred to mathematics performance.

Method overview

Forty-eight 2nd-grade middle-school students ($M_{age}=12.31$ years, $SD=0.59$) in Austria participated in the study. The intervention group consisted of 26 students (15 identified as female, 11 identified as male) while the control of 22 (16 female, 6 male). During a four-week intervention, students completed eight 15-minute spatial training sessions (two per week) in the RIF3.0 platform. Each session covered tasks from each of the following spatial skills: visualization, form constancy, position in space, transformation in space, and object combination. During that period, students in the control classes received mathematics instructions according to the mathematics curriculum. We assessed students' mathematics

skills one day before and after the intervention. For the assessment, we used a collection of arithmetical, place value, geometry, and word problem tasks, which we developed based on the description of mathematics competence provided by the Austrian Ministry of Education.

Key Findings

Students from the intervention group significantly improved their accuracy in the arithmetical and geometry tasks while students at the control group did not (Table 1). However, student's accuracy in the place value and word-problems tasks, both among the intervention and the control groups, was not improved (Table 1).

Table 1

Results of paired sample t-tests comparing students' scores in the pre and post-tests

Mathematics tasks	Group	Pre-test		Post-test		<i>t</i> (df)	<i>p</i>	Cohen's <i>d</i>
		<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
Arithmetical	Intervention	5.77	1.28	6.7	1.41	3.728(25)	< .001	0.731
	Control	6.27	1.28	6.05	1.81	-0.561(21)	0.581	-0.120
Place value	Intervention	4.54	1.14	4.64	1.45	0.667(25)	.511	0.131
	Control	4.91	1.10	4.60	1.14	-2.037	.054	-0.434
Geometry	Intervention	4.52	1.9	5.25	1.84	2.225(25)	0.035	0.436
	Control	4.18	2.46	4.16	2.78	-0.074(21)	0.941	-0.016
Word problem	Intervention	4.50	2.02	4.04	2.41	-1.312(25)	.202	-0.257
	Control	5.18	2.50	5.27	2.23	0.222(21)	.827	0.047

Conclusion

These findings suggest that training in a combination of spatial skills may lead to improved performance in arithmetical and geometry tasks but not in place-value and word-problem tasks. Unlike Hawes et al. (2015), our within-school intervention yielded positive mathematics-related outcomes, which are in line with the lab-based findings of Gilligan et al. (2020). In our study, we demonstrated that online training in multiple spatial skills within the mathematics classroom may contribute to curriculum-based mathematics improvement.

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